

Horizon 2020 Work programme

Food Security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland Water Research and the Bioeconomy

Call

H2020-FNR-2020: Food and Natural Resources

Topic name

FNR-16-2020: ENZYMES FOR MORE ENVIRONMENT-FRIENDLY CONSUMER PRODUCTS

FuturEnzyme:

Technologies of the Future for Low-Cost Enzymes for Environment-Friendly Products

Final ID: 101000327

SCIENCE, CONSUMER, POLICY BRIEFS: RESEARCH FOCUS

D8.17

SARA DANIOTTI, ILARIA RE, FEDERICA BINELLO
CONSORZIO ITALBIOTEC
ITALBIOTEC, VIA GAUDENZIO FANTOLI 16/15, 20138, MILAN (ITALY)

Document information sheet

Work package:	WP8, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Authors:	ITB (Sara Daniotti, Ilaria Re, Federica Binello), CSIC (Manuel Ferrer, Patricia Molina)
Document version:	1
Date:	31/05/2025
WP starting date:	01/06/2021
WP duration:	48 months
WP lead beneficiary:	ITB
WP participant(s):	CSIC as main contributor and all partners for providing feedback and suggestions for implementation
Deliv lead beneficiary:	ITB
Dissemination Level:	Public
Type	Report
Due date (months)	48
Contact details:	Sara Daniotti (sara.daniotti@italbiotec.it), Ilaria Re (ilaria.re@italbiotec.it), Federica Binello (federica.binello@italbiotec.it), Manuel Ferrer (mferrer@icp.csic.es), Patricia Molina (patricia.molina@icp.csic.es)

Summary

- 1. Scope of deliverable 4
- 2. Altroconsumo/Euroconsumers article 4
- 3. Consumer analysis 5
- 4. FuturEnzyme policy brief: a legacy 5
- 5. Conclusion 6

1. Scope of deliverable

This deliverable consists in a series of Science, Consumer, Policy Briefs through which to draft individual and common scientific, market, consumer, social, and policy advices within the consortium and in collaboration with other consortia (D8.21 is dedicated to inter-consortia policy briefs). This material is available through the website.

2. Altroconsumo/Euroconsumers article

The collaboration between [Altroconsumo/Euroconsumers](#) and FuturEnzyme comes from the beginning of the project. Luisa Crisigiovanni, member of this organization, is member of the [Advisory Board](#) of the project, and besides that, a collaboration was already stated in the Grant Agreement. As Altroconsumo and Euroconsumers are really well-known organizations by Italian and European consumers, respectively, this increased the impact that FuturEnzyme can have at consumers level, and maybe even reaching policy level. The collaboration has been materialized in tangible news and articles shared within Euroconsumers and Altroconsumo community and in particular:

- 1 [article](#), released on 20 March 2025, in English on Euroconsumers.org, meant to reach a multistakeholder audience from different European countries. On LinkedIn, Euroconsumers has over 7000 followers.
- 1 article in Italian on "AC Inchieste", more than 248,000 copies of "Altroconsumo Inchieste" distributed in 2023

PROGETTO UE

Futurenzyme, prodotti più sostenibili grazie agli enzimi

Sono un'alternativa efficace e green alle sostanze chimiche usate nell'industria. Siamo stati parte del progetto europeo per promuoverne le potenzialità.

► Luisa Crisigiovanni (responsabile Eu Fundraising & Projects Development per Altroconsumo ed Euroconsumers) è stata membro del comitato consultivo di FUTURENZYME, progetto dell'Unione europea per la promozione della tecnologia enzimatica come alternativa efficace e sostenibile alle sostanze chimiche nocive utilizzate per prodotti come detersivi, tessuti e cosmetici. Gli enzimi sono sostanze

naturali che possono infatti velocizzare i processi produttivi, riducendo l'uso di energia, le emissioni e gli sprechi di acqua. Lo scorso aprile il progetto si è concluso con un evento a Madrid in cui, insieme a decisori politici, industria e ricercatori, abbiamo esplorato le potenzialità innovative di queste biotecnologie per soddisfare la domanda di più prodotti ecosostenibili. Più informazioni su futurenzyme.eu

**Funded by
the European Union**

Questo progetto ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal programma di ricerca e innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione Europea nell'ambito dell'accordo di sovvenzione n. 101000327, i pareri e le opinioni espressi sono tuttavia solo quelli degli autori e non riflettono necessariamente quelli dell'Unione Europea.

- 1 online [news story](#) on the project goals and its first communicable results, published at the end of May 2025 - in 2023, 38 million views to the website - 914,000 users on social channels (40,000 X followers, 138,000 Instagram followers, 19,000 LinkedIn followers, 675,500 Facebook followers and 31,000 YouTube subscribers, 10,500 TikTok followers).

3. Consumer analysis

The project has a strong commitment to aligning scientific innovation with societal needs. In this line, an extensive social analysis was conducted to evaluate consumer preferences and perceptions in terms of sustainability in detergent, textile, and cosmetic products (coordinated by ITB partner) by using Choice Experiments (CEs), a methodology widely recognized for assessing real-life decision-making dynamics in consumer markets. CEs on the three product categories studied ([laundry detergents](#), polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics - publication in preparation for the latter two) allow not only to identify which specific sustainability attributes (e.g. biodegradability, carbon footprint reduction, eco-packaging, natural ingredient sourcing) carry the most value from a consumer perspective (design strategy), but also to quantify the willingness to pay for such features (market positioning strategy).

The outcome revealed that European consumers mind about the environmental footprint of their daily-use products and may support greener alternatives, provided information on transparency, accessible pricing, and demonstrable benefits in performance and environmental impact. The obtained results are also valuable for targeting innovation efforts toward attributes that line up with end users. Socioeconomic and demographic data were also noted, revealing the biases by age, gender, education level, and income, that prioritize certain sustainability features over others.

This information can help companies to select the most impactful product features, to tailor communication and pricing strategies, supporting innovation and commercial success. Moreover, by embedding social research into the innovation pipeline, FuturEnzyme reaffirms its commitment to responsible research and innovation (RRI), ensuring that the solutions it develops align with the values, expectations, and everyday choices of European consumers.

For specific results related to the detergent product, please refer to ITB's recent [publication](#). Results for the three products are also summarised in **D8.15**.

4. FuturEnzyme policy brief: a legacy

The consortium prepared a policy brief, which is part of the legacy of the project FuturEnzyme. The objective was to present, clearly and concisely, the most impactful knowledge gained throughout the project, along with its policy-related conclusions, targeting the general public, stakeholders, and policy makers. The main text was prepared by CSIC as coordinator, and was revised, completed and approved by all the partners. ITB helped in the initial preparation of the text and prepared the final document with the visual design.

It is entitled *FuturEnzyme Legacy - A Science-Policy Brief on Advancing Enzyme Technology for Greener Consumer Products*, and the structure is as follows:

- Introduction
- The power of enzymes
- Presentation of the targeted cleaner and more efficient consumer products (laundry detergents, textiles and cosmetics)
- Feedback from consumers
- Brief on the benefits and safety of enzymes

- Findings and facts produced along the project in relation to the benefits and safety of enzymes, consumers' views and preferences, and technology and market actual situation
- Policy takeaways, with views and recommendations from our companies' experts on the actual state of the enzymatic market and regulations
- Conclusions
- References
- Links to more project's information
- FuturEnzyme's partners

Along the text, there are quotes from companies' experts on the issue, reinforcing the message in different aspects.

All the images used come from the partners, and their real facilities and/or products.

Since it was released in May 2025, at the end of the project, there has been no opportunity to promote it at any project event. However, it is currently being advertised through partners' newsletters (e.g. CLIB's), social media, and to Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) and EU Policymakers.

The document, shown as it is in the following pages, is publicly available through [FuturEnzyme's Zenodo community](#) and the [project's website](#) (linked to Zenodo).

To reinforce the impact of this Science–Consumer–Policy Brief, a short [video](#) was also produced and distributed through the same channels, including during the [Info Day](#).

5. Conclusion

In this document, it is stated how the project has prepared different actions directed to learn from and inform society, consumers, and policy-makers, using a solid scientific ground. Through an article about the project in a broad audience consumer platform, three choice experiments on the project targeted consumer products, and a policy brief, the consortium has gathered valuable information of the real consumer needs as well as inform of enzyme benefits and safety, so we can consider this deliverable as achieved.